

RESOURCE MANAGEMENT CYCLES

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Annotation: this article covers human resource management cycles, a strategic and logically consistent approach to Personnel Management at the enterprise, the stages of the life cycle of employees, types of human capital cycles, concepts on concept.

Keywords: Human Resources, Capital, Management, cycles, personnel, enterprise, approach, position, professional development, intensive, labor.

Human Resource Management as the most valuable asset of an enterprise can be defined as a strategic and logically consistent approach to Personnel Management. K. Fambren and other representatives of the Michigan School of management have noted in their works that the human resource cycle consists of four main processes or functions that are performed at any enterprise): selection (ensuring that existing human resources correspond to workplaces); certification (performance management activities); salary (management tool system used to stimulate performance; it should encourage short-term and long-term achievements); development (training of high-quality employees).

M.A. Vinokurov and N.A. In their scientific work, gorelovs highlight the stages of the life cycle of employees - identifying the need for personnel, searching and hiring personnel, professional guidance and training of qualified personnel, professional selection, personnel placement and professional flexibility, certification and evaluation of personnel, formation of reserves, promotion, replacement of personnel, retraining and professional development and dismissal.

A.I. Dobrinin, S.A. Dyatlov and E.D. The increase in human capital by tsirenovas is a multi-stage process, which, on the one hand, involves the stages of functional turnover (investments, accumulation of potential, its application in the labor process, the growth of labor productivity, income and other influences, an increase in the interest of human capital in new investments), and, on the other hand, the stages of natural, economic and, in the context of high-tech upgrades, there is a focus on the work of workers to get a new profession.

S.A. Dyatlov, L.G. Simkina and I.V. Skoblyakovas distinguish three types of human capital cycles, which differ in direction, volume and types of investments: 1) a long cycle (50-60 years) as a form of National Human Capital reproduction, in which

needs and production change dramatically; 2) an average cycle (10-12 years) means of Labor increase the human capital of an enterprise during a generation of implementation; 3) a

Combining the concepts of human capital turnover with the concepts of knowledge and the life cycle of human resources, the life cycle of human capital of an enterprise can be determined by achieving the goals set by the enterprise as a period of time from the emergence of the need for human capital to the age retirement of human capital, formed for natural reasons or in The process of accumulating and using human capital during this cycle

1. Determination of the need for human capital (in quantitative and qualitative terms).
2. Formation of human capital at the expense of external and internal resources (Search, Selection, Recruitment, Recruitment, vocational guidance and training in educational institutions, adaptation, transfer and placement of personnel from other departments, including costs).
3. The development of human capital, which traditionally involves the individual and organizational training of employees with potential, the processes of planning and organizing their career growth. This stage involves the accumulation of the intellectual and creative potential of the employees of the enterprise and the increase in the value of the existing human capital.
4. At the stage of using and maintaining human capital, which includes ensuring normal working conditions and safety, assessing indicators in labor and the workplace, material and intangible wages of employees and Social Security corresponding to the value of their human capital, enterprises and employees receive income from investments in human capital in the form of increased labor productivity, competitiveness and income. In Practice, 3-4 stages are usually performed parallellously.
5. The outflow of human capital due to its natural, economic and innovative turnover will have to dismiss employees in connection with retirement, or because their profession or qualifications do not correspond to the new requirements of the enterprise. If the enterprise strategy does not provide for business reduction, then the fifth stage proceeds logically with a repetition of the cycle (instead of Retired Employees, new employees are accepted or jobs are reorganized).

In any case, the beginning of the next reproductive cycle encourages the enterprise to invest new investments in human capital, and in order to maintain the competitiveness of the enterprise, it is advisable to start this new cycle before the fifth stage.

It is recommended to consider investments in the human capital of the enterprise as all expenses for the formation, maintenance and development of human capital, which are carried out at all stages of its life cycle and are aimed at increasing the competitiveness of the enterprise, regardless of the intensity and time of costs.

Thus, investments in human assets are not limited to the costs of training employees, but also include the costs of search, selection, adaptation, promotion, employee promotion, and labor protection. The use of this approach makes it possible to more accurately determine the amount of investment costs and the value of human capital, as well as more efficiently manage the processes of its accumulation.

P.N. Zavlin, S.V. Ermasov, N.B. Ermasova and N.I. Lukicheva in the works of the authors reflects the balanced development of human capital and the problems of ensuring the innovative activity of the enterprise, as well as approaches to solving these problems using personnel management tools (organization and promotion of Labor, methods of socio-psychological management, development of employee competencies), but not investments in human assets, but in this regard, the task, it is noted that it is of methodological and practical interest.

At the level of an individual enterprise, a synchronous approach is preferable, taking into account the development of new processes as an integral part of the production of new products (services). In accordance with this approach, it can be assumed that the life cycle of a certain element of the human capital of an enterprise should more or less coincide with the life cycle of an innovational product created by this capital (if some stages of these cycles proceed almost completely synchronously, while others partially correspond). The investment cycle in this case is unusual: the investment and operation stages will be interconnected at the stages of application, storage and partial disposal of human assets, since investments in human capital are not limited only to its formation and development. The maximum profitability of investments is manifested at the stages of growth and maturity of innovations.

Thus, the Human Resource Management Concept provides a theoretical and methodological basis for managing the value of human capital of an enterprise, and the knowledge management concept provides an increase in the value of human assets (their ability to produce new knowledge). But neither one nor the other has a sufficiently complete idea of the mechanisms for ensuring the effectiveness of investments in the assets of this type of enterprise on their own, the choice of economically optimal ways to convert the value of human capital into the value of the organization. It can be seen that to solve the structured task, it is necessary to use other areas of Management, in particular, investment management, which, by

definition, is the management of all aspects of the investment activity of the business entity.

However, in the theory, methodology and practice of investment management, investments in human capital are not given enough attention - they are not an independent direction of the investment strategy of the enterprise, but an element of costs within the framework of Real investment projects. In this regard, it is necessary that the theoretical and methodological rules on which management decisions are made on investments in human capital in an enterprise are developed from the point of view of a systematic approach.

Today, the main relevance of scientific research work is the increase in the profitability of investments in human capital.

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